

DAIRY PRODUCTS AND THE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

Doru NECULA ^{1,2}, Octavia Maria TAMAS-KRUMPE ^{2*} și Brîndușa COVACI ¹

¹ Mountain Economy Center, "CE-MONT", "Costin C. Kirițescu" NIER, Romanian Academy, Petreni St., no. 49, 725700, Vatra Dornei, Romania

² University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Cluj-Napoca, Mănăștur St., no.3-5, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

*Corresponding author: octavia.tamas@usamvcluj.ro

Abstract

Around the world, agriculture is of the greatest importance because it produces food for animals and people. Livestock is the branch that produces milk and meat, which are essential for human consumption. It is followed by the dairy industry, whose products are an important source of nutrients for human nutrition. All these activities are energy-intensive. Cultivation of the land, then harvesting, feeding and caring for animals, milk production, milk transportation and processing are dependent on electricity and the oil industry. These activities are indispensable for food production, but they have a major impact on the environment by increasing the carbon footprint and thus greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. For this review, we have set out to discuss and raise awareness among the general public and those practicing agriculture that the livestock and dairy industries are a major source of GHGs. This is why it is necessary to take measures to mitigate these sources by implementing strategies to reduce and balance them, to find strategies, without giving up these activities, but to make them as profitable as possible. In animal husbandry, the water footprint can be controlled by choosing appropriate feed rations, while in the dairy industry the largest amount of water is represented by wastewater and with a high energy consumption. However, an alternative source of energy at the farm level is the anaerobic digestion of manure and obtaining energy generated by methane and transformed into electricity. Also, by installing solar panels at the farm level and in the processing industry, it would lead to reducing GHG emissions. Climate change brought about by GHGs has led to higher temperatures and a lack of rainfall, which will in time lead to a shortage of the water so necessary for agriculture and the processing industry.

Keywords: *Animal husbandry; dairy; carbon; water; energy; pollution; greenhouse gases.*

INTRODUCTION

Dairy products are foods for which demand is increasing, with demand expected to double by 2050 due to global population growth as well as income growth (Alexandratos and Bruinsma, 2012). It is estimated that by 2050 the global population will be around 9.8 billion people, who over time will switch to diets increasingly rich in animal products, especially dairy (Gerber et al. 2013; Gerbens-Leenes, 2017). Their production involves the use of large amounts of resources such as: agricultural land, agricultural crops, water, oil, with major impacts in the production of greenhouse gases (GHG) (Notarnicola et al. 2017).

Currently the biggest concerns facing society are climate change (Steffen et al. 2007; Flysjö, 2011). Global greenhouse gas emissions are also represented by the food industry sector, which accounts for a significant share of about one third of total emissions (Barker, 2007; Flysjö, 2011). In the dairy and dairy processing sector, related to production, transportation, processing, it is estimated that gas emissions comprise about 2.7 of the total global greenhouse gas emissions (Gerber et al. 2010; Notarnicola et al. 2017).

Milk is an important and rich source of nutrients for human nutrition, but its quality starts to deteriorate immediately after milking due to the growth of pathogenic microorganisms. In order to maintain its freshness, milk needs to be cooled to around 3-4°C, after which it can be transported over longer distances to processing plants. For processing, milk sometimes has to be heated to pasteurization temperatures and then cooled again, thus consuming a large amount of energy and thus increasing carbon dioxide emissions (Debnath et al. 2022). In order to reduce energy consumption, the use of environmentally friendly procedures such as radio frequency processing, pulsed ultraviolet light, ultrasound, irradiation, high pressure technology, ozone treatment, pulsed electric field, and other less energy consuming methods have been started (Singh and Debanth, 2019; Hazra et al. 2020; Debnath et al. 2022). Also long time ripening of cheeses results in high energy consumption as they have to be kept for 6-8 months and even longer at low temperatures to get the specific flavor. Enzymes such as lipase, esterase and protease can be used to speed up the ripening and flavor of cheeses and reduce energy consumption (Law, 2001; Debnath et al. 2022).

The dairy industry also results in many by-products such as casein and caseinate that can be incorporated into other food products that will increase their protein content (Badem and Uçar 2017). Badem and Uçar (2017) specify that from industrial casein can be obtained adhesives, paints or rubber. Barukčić et al. (2014) in his research highlights another valuable product such as whey obtained from cheese making which can be used in making whey powder, whey protein concentrate, lactose powder, baker's yeast, soft drinks which are rich in electrolytes, or ethanol, biogas, etc. Also the addition of buttermilk powder to yogurt prevents syneresis due to its high water binding capacity (Garczewska-Murzyn et al. 2022)

In this context, the aim of the present work was to highlight the environmental impacts of the livestock and dairy processing industry on the environment, based on the work in the literature.

METHODOLOGY

Being a bibliographic work, no original experimental research was carried out. In order to carry out this bibliographic study, we consulted a set of bibliographic sources, including recent or older scientific publications, but established in the field addressed. At the same time, we resorted to accessing online some highly topical scientific documentation platforms (Google Scholar/Academic, Web of Science), using the following search terms: "greenhouse gases", "carbon footprint", "pollution in animal husbandry systems", "pollution in the dairy industry". The synthesized data was descriptively processed and comparatively analyzed, and then assembled and organized in the following chapters.

Use of preservatives in dairy processing

Web (2022) states that about more than 800 million people globally are starving given that at the same time each year FAO (2011) claims that about 1.3 million tons of products are spoiled, the most significant being dairy waste (Gustafsson et al. 2013; Debnath et al. 2022). Increasing the shelf life of products can be improved through bio-

preservatives that do not harm either human health or the environment. Among them we can mention: essential oils, nisin, lactacin, pedocin which have bacteriostatic or bactericidal effects and at the same time influence the maintenance of the products' organoleptic and physico-chemical qualities (Debnath et al. 2022). Nisin has as source *Lactococcus lacticus, subsp. lactis* with application in pasteurized milk and processed cheese with effects on the inhibition of *Clostridium tirobutyricum* (Khurana and Kanawjia, 2007). Lactacinin has as source *Lactococcus lactis*, having a role in accelerating the ripening of cheeses but also in eliminating some gram positive microorganisms (Guinane et al. 2005; Sen and Ray, 2019). The pedocin produced by *Lactobacillus plantarum* has a particularly inhibitory effect against *Listeria monocytogenes* in cottage cheese and ice cream (Rodríguez et al. 2002; Debnath et al. 2022).

Among the essential oils, cumin, rosemary and thyme inhibit the growth of pathogens such as *Salmonella typhi* and *Bacillus cereus*, and also play an important role in maintaining the organoleptic and physicochemical properties of soft cheeses (EL-Kholy and Amer 2017; Mishra et al. 2020). Zataria, mint and basil together have a role in preventing the growth of *Escherichia coli* and *Listeria monocytogenes* in yogurts (Azizkhani and Tooryan, 2016). Cumin and thyme are considered as veritable bacteriophages that act as antioxidants in preventing the denaturation of butter during butter storage, while also preventing the growth of *Salmonella spp.* microorganisms, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Listeria monocytogene*, and the development of endolysins in milk and cheese (El-Sayed and Youssef 2019; Ameer et al. 2019).

The water footprint

Although it contributes to the prosperity and health of humanity, freshwater consumption, along with land use, fossil fuel consumption, and other polluting compounds that lead to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, is one of the main environmental aspects for which agricultural production is responsible (Mekonnen and Gerbens-Leenes, 2020).

It is less well known that feed production is facing increasing demands for water as climate change will cause a water crisis. It is for this reason that the need to mitigate negative impacts in food production with environmental impacts is emerging (Thornton, 2010). Of all branches of the economy, agriculture has become the largest consumer of water, and water scarcity in the future may lead to impacts on the production of food needed by the population (Godfray et al. 2010; Strzepek and Boehlert, 2010). Rising temperatures coupled with decreasing precipitation will greatly affect the water cycle leading to increasing water scarcity (Rojas-Downing et al. 2017). Amid these changes, plant evapotranspiration will increase significantly, reportedly because crop plants will consume more water (Guzmán-Luna et al. 2022). Increased global population levels will raise competition for water and energy (Thornton, 2010). Excessive water use is associated with the risk of water contamination, with salt and nitrates being the most common groundwater contaminants (Grout et al. 2006). Also, globally, livestock accounts for about one third of the water footprint (Mekonnen and Hoekstra, 2012) and of this footprint, 98% is water needed to produce animal feed (Shiklomanov, 2000).

As milk production increases, the water footprint will decrease in favor of the carbon footprint (Mekonnen and Hoekstra, 2012). In a study, Hoekstra (2012) concludes that diets with more forages reduce the water footprint in milk production and the use of

concentrates in feed increases the water footprint about 5 times more than fibrous feeds. In this context, it is recommended to choose feed rations for animal feed that decrease the water footprint. The largest amount of water is wastewater in the dairy industry, which is energy intensive (Drożdźiel et al. 2017). In the dairy industry, large amounts of water are used for each production step, starting from raw milk that is heat treated and then cooled, where 2-3 times water is consumed for 1L of milk that is heat treated and then cooled (Singh and Kumar, 2009). In 2018, Klemes et al. reported that about 10.8 L milk is used for 1 kg of dairy product obtained. The wastewater from dairy processing will increase the organic load in the sewage system and at the same time greatly reduce the oxygen content in the reservoir water, seriously affecting the life of aquatic life (Al-Wasify et al. 2018). Wastewater treatment should be done as judiciously as possible because it can contribute to the emission of greenhouse gases through the release of carbon and methane (Keller, J. and Hartley, 2003).

Agricultural land use and climate in the current context

Agricultural history has shown that it has always responded to increased demand for food by expanding and developing new areas for production. Given global population growth trends this option is out of date (Smith et al. 2010). Godfray (2010) argues that reclaiming some land for agricultural land return is at the expense of forest deforestation with repercussions and at the expense of biodiversity, which can contribute to the greenhouse gas footprint. When the land is not suitable for cereal cultivation, it is used for grazing, becoming more suitable for livestock production and then for human food without competing with food from cereal fed livestock (Capper et al. 2009). Another study by Mekonnen and Hoekstra (2012) reported that the water footprint for dairy products is lower from a mixed feeding system i.e. grazing system with industrial products, considering optimal land use and availability of water sources. Dairy from mountain pastures also stimulates tourism and recreational activities, and these activities accompanied with animal welfare have favored the establishment of organic markets stimulating farmers' activities (Meul et al. 2012). Due to climate change, the vegetation characteristic of each season will be affected by a delay or advancement of harvesting periods (Guzmán-Luna et al. 2022). These changes will alter the course of the seasons by deregulating the vegetation periods of some crops, with positive effects in some areas or negative in others (Guzmán-Luna et al. 2022).

Since the year 2000, global average temperatures have increased by 0.2-0.6 °C and are expected to increase by a further 1.5 to 5.8 °C by the end of the century (IPCC, 2007). Droughts will become increasingly difficult to withstand and extreme precipitation more frequent (Battisti and Naylor, 2009; Karl et al. 2009). In this case, dairy cows are facing heat stress (Ravagnolo et al. 2000) and therefore the breeding of more resistant breeds adapted to high temperatures is recommended, such as in Romania, the Transylvanian Pinzgau breed and Pinzgau with the Black and Brown Maramureş variety (Necula et al. 2024). In this context, new challenges in dairy production are emerging, stimulating the use of pastures that can constitute a diversification of farming systems (Sanderson et al. 2009).

In recent centuries, land-use change measures have been taken with very large repercussions on ecological stability, sometimes greater than climate change. However,

most land-use change measures are not always related to climate change or even climate, and thus people will change land use and management to adapt to climate change, which could amplify some ecological effects (Dale, 1997).

Energy consumption

The dairy industry is dependent on non-renewable resources considerably increasing its carbon footprint and is therefore considered unsustainable (Godfray et al. 2010). Milk processing technology involves the use of mechanical processes such as homogenization, emulsification, stirring, centrifugation, preparation for curdling (in the case of cheese) which consume electricity (Dąbrowski et al. 2021). Planting of crops, fertilization, harvesting and delivery of feed depend on the oil industry (Von Keyserlingk et al. 2013). In mountain areas where animals are not permanently kept in closed stalls and are taken out to pasture, the dependence on oil is greatly reduced. This is true of indigenous breeds that are more resilient in the grazing system, but the same cannot be said for cows with genetics geared to record milk production. Das et al. (2001) mentions grazing systems that are less dependent on a share of energy in that cows consume grass, fertilize with their own manure, and the sun's rays convert it all into milk. An alternative source of on-farm energy that could mitigate the dependence on non-renewable energy and should be considered could be the fermentation of manure and obtaining methane-generated energy (Zaks et al. 2011; Atandi and Rahman, 2022). Another alternative to renewable energy is the installation of solar panels on dairy farms. By anaerobically digesting the manure and obtaining biogas they can reduce GHG emissions both during storage and when administered on the fertilizer field benefiting the decrease of CH₄ emissions (Aguirre-Villegas et al. 2015). Also, by producing renewable energy from manure and reducing gas, the sustainability of the farm is improved (Lijó et al. 2017), and by converting gas into electricity as well as utilizing photovoltaic system which is converted from solar energy into electricity (Peng et al. 2013), the farm becomes a producer of electricity instead of a consumer, thus reducing CO₂ emissions (Bey et al. 2016; Peng et al. 2013).

Fertilizer management

Manure includes handling, collection and storage, factors that contribute to GHG emissions that represent at the level of a dairy farm about 9-15% carbon footprint (Roibás et al. 2016; Noya et al. 2018). The main source of N₂O emissions is manure (Guzmán-Luna et al. 2022). Also depending on climatic conditions, during handling and storage, manure also releases a certain amount of CH₄. To estimate the emissions of N₂O and CH₄, Guzmán-Luna et al. (2022) used default emission factors proposed in 2006 by the IPCC. Manure is considered as the best natural fertilizer for providing nutrients for growing crops but also for grassland. However, applied in excess, it has the reverse effect through nutrient loss, surface and groundwater contamination and air pollution (Knowlton et al. 2004).

The livestock sector, through livestock farming, has been identified as an important source of N and P contamination of surface waters (Smith and Alexander, 2000). It is precisely for this reason that public concern about water quality has greatly increased leading to the implementation of legislative regulations (Knowlton et al. 2004). Thus, some countries have already taken measures to reduce losses from grade litter by

developing platforms to reduce N and P runoff from surface waters (Von Keyserlingk et al. 2013).

Air pollution

The second largest contributor of greenhouse gases (GHGs) globally is considered to be agriculture at 26%, followed then by electricity and heat production at 25% (Meena et al. 2022). According to US EPA (2012), agriculture contributes 16.3 to the total GHG emissions and the emission from dairy production is about 1 kg carbon dioxide Eq/Kg milk at the farm gate (FAO, 2010). Of the total on-farm emissions CH₄ is the largest contributor and originates from rumen enteric fermentation (Hagemann et al. 2011), and is 25 times more GHG than CO₂ for the environment (IPCC, 2006).

The main sources of gaseous emissions at farm level are the feeding system, manure, animal housing, manure application on the ground, and the main gaseous pollutants are carbon dioxide (CO₂), nitrous oxide (N₂O) together with nitrogen acids (NO and NO₂), methane (CH₄), ammonia (NH₃), hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) and volatile organic compounds (VOCs), (Von Keyserlingk et al. 2013). So to produce milk and milk by-products the environmental impact is quite significant (Alvarado et al. 2012; Von Keyserlingk et al. 2013). Von Keyserlingk et al. (2013) specifies that monitoring the animal production as closely as possible, managing very carefully the characteristics of the farm floors and the frequency of cleaning, managing as responsibly as possible the aerobic and anaerobic compost, will allow the mitigation of the gas emissions to reach a specific acceptable variable, in order to identify the best strategies to go ahead and obtain milk and dairy products in accordance with veterinary health regulations.

Carbon footprint

By and large, environmental concerns are becoming increasingly widespread in both the press and academia. The amounts of energy consumed to produce a product will be transformed and interpreted into accessible impact indicators (Meena et al. 2022). In the case of milk and dairy production, the only impact category is the global warming potential, reported as CO₂ equivalent/kilogram of milk over a 100-year period (Foster, 2013), where 1 kg CO₂ = 1 kg CO₂ equivalent (Eq), 1 kg CH₄ = 25 kg CO₂Eq, 1 kg N₂O = 298 kg CO₂ Eq (Meena et al. 2022). Thus, the global warming potential is estimated for each type of gas based on its heating power and atmospheric lifetime. Often however these results are subjective. But since the dairy industry is a major source of greenhouse gases (GHGs), it is necessary to identify the critical points in order to implement mitigation strategies by increasing animal productivity and improving reproductive quality, and also to research as efficiently as possible on the production of feed and feed additives (Meena et al. 2022).

The carbon footprint is the total greenhouse gas emissions accumulated over a staged period of production of a product, measured in CO₂ equivalent (Meena et al. 2022). The carbon footprint of milk (Table 1) is calculated using life-cycle assessment (LCA) to highlight the efficiency of the production system in obtaining and valorizing milk (Mazzetto et al. 2022). The production of milk and dairy products needs to be assessed with particular attention, as it is an important source of elements vital for human consumption (Vida and Tedesco, 2017).

Table 1. Carbon footprint for milk production (1 kg) in different countries

Country	Farm type	Carbon footprint (KgCO ₂ eq)	Reference
Columbia	Mixt production (milk-meat)	2.1-4.2	(Gonzalez-Quintero et al. 2021)
Uruguay	Milk production	0.97	(Darre et al. 2021)
New Zealand	Milk production	0.78	(Ledgard et al. 2020)
Kenya	Small-scale milk production	2.19-3.13	(Wilkes et al. 2020)
China	Milk production	1.34	(Wang et al. 2018)
Australia	Milk production	0.39-1.35	(Sejian et al. 2018)
Ireland	Milk production	1.22	(Yan et al. 2013)
Ireland	Grazed animals	1.11	(O'Brien et al. 2014)
Portugal	Grazed animals	0.83	(Morais et al.2018)
Italy	Milk production	1.12	(Bacenetti et al. 2016)
Australia	Milk production	1.11	(Gollnow et al. 2014)
Canada	Milk production	0.44 - 1.73	(Jayasundara et al. 2019)

For a better sustainability of dairy producing farms it is necessary to implement the most eligible strategies to reduce GHG, such as CH₄, N₂O and CO₂ (Vida and Tedesco, 2017). Gerber et al. (2013) predict that GHG emissions could be reduced in the livestock sector by about 30% by applying the best technologies and practices in the sector. Through on-farm change and modernization, GHG emissions can be considerably reduced through well applied management (Castro et al. 2012). A reduced number of animals with increased productivity can also be a way to reduce CH₄ (Moss et al. 2000). Maintaining a healthy status of cows by preventing diseases such as mastitis will reduce non-productive periods, reduce CH₄/liter of milk and at the same time reduce GHG emissions (Garnsworthy, 2004).

DISCUSSIONS

Studies conducted by more and more researchers are focused on mitigating the effects of GHG.

Animal feed, by making it more efficient, can be a particularly important factor in the emissions produced by animals. The relationship between the ability to achieve increased productivity and GHG emissions has been demonstrated especially in the dairy sector by the fact that per kg of milk, emissions have decreased considerably with the increase in animal productivity.

If we consider the mountain area, GHG emissions are considerably reduced by feeding animals on pastures. This increases the digestibility coefficient of the feed, related to an improvement in health and well-being, which leads to an increase in reproductive efficiency with greater productivity, and overall to a reduction in the carbon footprint.

Grazing ensures the truest welfare of animals, which is also considered the best strategy to reduce the carbon footprint. Many studies focused on farm management regarding animal productivity show that there are large differences between farms, in relation to animal productivity and environmental performance.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we aimed to analyze and define the main factors in the dairy industry that interact with global climate change. Thus, we provide information on how the sustainability of the dairy sector in the short and long term will be seriously disrupted by the effects of climate change. Dairy products are staple foods in the human diet, and their consumption increases with population growth. Food production also involves the use of large quantities of energy resources with major effects on the increase in the carbon footprint and implicitly on the increase in greenhouse gases that have led to considerable climate change over time. However, the production of milk and dairy products must be evaluated with particular care, as it constitutes an important source of vital elements for human consumption.

Due to these climate changes, seasons are disrupted, water shortages occur, with an impact on crops. With the increase in climate change, a series of microorganisms will proliferate that will affect the quality of milk and dairy products, food safety will be affected and waste generated by the dairy industry could increase. In this context, the future of the planet is full of uncertainties, and this work urges making clear decisions and establishing concrete strategies in animal husbandry and the dairy industry. Through well-implemented farm management modernization, GHG emissions could be significantly reduced. Reducing the number of animals and exploiting those with high productivity can be an alternative to reduce CH₄.

It can be argued that the findings of many researchers, although approximate, highlight the importance of considering all GHGs and highlight that the practices that best reduce emissions may also vary depending on location. From many points of view, greenhouse gas emissions constitute a new global challenge, but more extensive and thorough research can lead to more efficient and better activities and practices that help to perform the reduction of production externalities.

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